

AMORPHOPHALLUS KONJAC AS A PHARMACOLOGICAL TOOL

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The cob is shorter or much longer than the bedspread. Plants are monoecious. The female zone is shorter, equal or longer than the male zone. The male zone is cylindrical, ellipsoid, conical or obverse-conical, usually adjacent to the female, sometimes separated by a sterile zone, which may be smooth or consist of prismatic, hemispherical or bristle-like sterile flowers. At the end of the cob there is usually a sterile appendage, sometimes absent or reduced to the size of a stump, vertical, sometimes horizontal, occasionally hanging down, very variable in shape, usually more or less conical or cylindrical, occasionally more or less spherical, sometimes stalked or narrowed at the base, usually smooth or composed of staminate structures at the base or completely covered with staminodes, sometimes wrinkled, occasionally pubescent, sometimes strongly and unevenly flattened.

Flowers monoecious, without perianth. Male flower: 1-6 stamens, free or fused at the flowers located at the base of the cob, or all of them, short; threads are missing or not; the binder is quite thick; thecae are obovate or oblong, located opposite each other, burst with apical (occasionally lateral) pores or a transverse incision. Pollen in pollinia, mostly ellipsoid to oblong-ellipsoid, sometimes spherical or hemispherical, medium to large (53 μm); exine striated, striated-reticulate, with tubercles or spines.

Female flower: gynoecium usually cramped, sometimes more or less spaced; ovary from hemispherical to ovoid or obovate, one-four-locular; in the nest, one anatropic ovule; funiculus very short to prominent vertical; placenta from axial to basal; style absent, short to very long, conical to cylindrical; stigma of various shapes, or spherical, or 2-4-lobed, star-shaped or occasionally punctate, sometimes large and brightly colored.

Pollination. As soon as the cob opens, pollination should occur on the same day. The inflorescence often emits the smell of decaying flesh to attract insects, however, there are some species of *Amorphophallus* that give off a pleasant smell. Caught in clever traps, insects are inside the cob in order to save the pollen they brought for female flowers. The female flowers remain open for only one day, while the male flowers remain closed. They open the next day, when the female flowers are no longer receptive, to avoid self-pollination. The male flowers drop

their pollen on the insects they catch, after which the insects are released, and can pollinate another flower. Amorphophalluses are used as food by some Lepidoptera larvae.

Practical use. Amorphophallus tubers are widely used in traditional Japanese cuisine to make soups or add to stews. They are also used to make noodle flour and a gelatin-like substance, which is then used to make special. In medicine, amorphophallus tubers are used as a raw material for the manufacture of diabetic products.

Использованная литература:

1. Аморфофаллус // Энциклопедический словарь Брокгауза и Ефрона : в 86 т. (82 т. и 4 доп.). — СПб., 1890—1907.
2. Ароидные // Ангола — Барзас. — М. : Советская энциклопедия, 1970. — (Большая советская энциклопедия : [в 30 т.] / гл. ред. А. М. Прохоров ; 1969—1978, т. 2).
3. Ароидеи // Энциклопедический словарь Брокгауза и Ефрона : в 86 т. (82 т. и 4 доп.). — СПб., 1890—1907.
4. Грудзинская И. А. Семейство ароидные (Araceae) // Жизнь растений. В 6-ти т. Т. 6. Цветковые растения / Под ред. А. Л. Тахтаджяна. — М.: Просвещение, 1982. — С. 466—493.
5. Чуб В. Загадки ароидных // Цветоводство. — 2008. — № 3. — С. 58—61.

